

Part I: Research Question

Can we train the time-series model using the history of revenues to forecast and predict future revenues?

This Data analytics study aims to prepare the history of revenues data and train the time-series model to predict and forecast future revenue.

Part II: Method Justification

Assumptions: Data stationarity is the common assumption in time series, a stationary process has the property that the mean, variance, and autocorrelation structure do not change over time. Stationarity can be defined in precise mathematical terms, but for our purpose, we mean a flat-looking series, without trend, constant variance over time, a constant autocorrelation structure over time, and no periodic fluctuations. (NIST 2021)

Autocorrelation is the coefficient of correlation between two values in the time series. (PSU 2021)

Part III: Data Preparation

The data preparation process

In [636...]

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
%matplotlib inline
import seaborn as sns
from dateutil.parser import parse
from statsmodels.tsa.stattools import adfuller
from statsmodels.tsa.seasonal import seasonal_decompose
from statsmodels.graphics.tsaplots import plot_acf, plot_pacf
import statsmodels.api as sm
from statsmodels.tsa.arima.model import ARIMA
from pandas import DataFrame
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error
from math import sqrt
from pmdarima import auto_arima
from statsmodels.tools.eval_measures import rmse
```

In [637...]

```
# Load the data set.
df = pd.read_csv(r"teleco_time_series .csv", index_col='Day')

df.index=pd.to_datetime(df.index, unit = 'D', origin = '2020-01-01')

df.index = pd.DatetimeIndex(df.index.values,
                             freq=df.index.inferred_freq)
```

```
# remove nulls
df=df.dropna()

# check if duplication
df.duplicated().any()

df.describe()
```

Out[637... **Revenue**

count	731.000000
mean	9.822901
std	3.852645
min	0.000000
25%	6.872836
50%	10.785571
75%	12.566911
max	18.154769

In [638... *# Plot and show the time series on axis ax1*

```
fig, ax1 = plt.subplots()
df.plot(figsize=(15, 4), ax=ax1)
plt.show()
```


In [639... `df.info`

```
<bound method DataFrame.info of Revenue
2020-01-02    0.000000
2020-01-03    0.000793
2020-01-04    0.825542
2020-01-05    0.320332
2020-01-06    1.082554
...
2021-12-28   16.931559
2021-12-29   17.490666
2021-12-30   16.803638
2021-12-31   16.194813
2022-01-01   16.620798
```

[731 rows x 1 columns]>

The Time Step Format:

2 columns and 731 rows (days), no Gaps between the data and the frequency are perfect.

```
In [640... # Evaluating the Stationarity Run the ADF test on the time series
result = adfuller(df['Revenue'])
# Print the test statistic and the p-value
print('ADF Statistic:', result[0])
print('p-value:', result[1])
print('critical values', result[4])
```

```
ADF Statistic: -1.9246121573101849
p-value: 0.3205728150793957
critical values {'1%': -3.4393520240470554, '5%': -2.8655128165959236, '10%': -2.568855736949163}
```

```
In [641... # Making the time series stationary
df_stationary = df.diff().dropna()
```

```
In [642... # Show after Making the time series stationary
fig, ax1 = plt.subplots()
df_stationary.plot(figsize=(15, 4), ax=ax1)
plt.show()
```



```
In [643... # Evaluating the Stationarity again
result = adfuller(df_stationary['Revenue'])
# Print the test statistic and the p-value
print('ADF Statistic:', result[0])
print('p-value:', result[1])
print('critical values', result[4])
```

```
ADF Statistic: -44.87452719387599
p-value: 0.0
critical values {'1%': -3.4393520240470554, '5%': -2.8655128165959236, '10%': -2.568855736949163}
```

```
In [644... # Save copy of Cleaned dataset
df_stationary.to_csv('prepared_clean_dataset.csv')
```

```
In [645... # Split the data into a train and test set
```

```
df_train = df_stationary.loc[:'6-30-2021']
df_test = df_stationary.loc['7-1-2021':]

# Create an axis
fig, ax = plt.subplots()

# Plot the train and test sets on the axis ax
df_train.plot(label = 'Train', figsize=(15, 4), ax=ax)
df_test.plot(label = 'Test', figsize=(15, 4), ax=ax)
ax.legend(labels=['Train', 'Test'])
plt.show()
```


Part IV: Model Identification and Analysis

Analyze the time series dataset:

In [646...

```
# Run autocorrelation coefficient with 50 days lag
autocorrelation_50 = df['Revenue'].autocorr(lag=50)
print("50 days: ", autocorrelation_50)
decompose=seasonal_decompose(df_stationary['Revenue'], period=50)
decompose.plot()
plt.show()
```

50 days: 0.822500880288965

In [647...

```
# Seasonal Plot
decompose.seasonal.plot(figsize=(15, 5))
```

Out[647... <AxesSubplot:>


```
In [648... # Trend Plot
decompose.trend.plot(figsize=(15, 5))
```

Out[648... <AxesSubplot:>


```
In [649... # Seasonal Plot
decompose.resid.plot(figsize=(15, 5))
```

Out[649... <AxesSubplot:>


```
In [650... # Autocorrelation Plot
fig, ax1 = plt.subplots()
fig = plot_acf(df_stationary['Revenue'], ax=ax1)
```

```
fig.set_size_inches(15, 5)
plt.show(fig)
```


In [651...

```
# Partial Autocorrelation Plot
fig, ax1 = plt.subplots()
fig = plot_pacf(df_stationary['Revenue'], ax=ax1)
fig.set_size_inches(15, 5)
plt.show(fig)
```


In [652...

```
df_sd= df_stationary.copy()
df_sd['Revenue_7_mean']= df_sd['Revenue'].rolling(window=7).mean()
df_sd.plot(figsize=(15, 5))
plt.show()
```


Spectral Density

the Spectral density represents the frequency domain of a time series. Which could view as a group of line waves.(line changes)

In [533...]

```
# Fit auto_arima to dataset (best model AR and MA)
auto_arima_fit = auto_arima(df_stationary['Revenue'], start_P=1,
                             start_q=1,
                             max_p=5,
                             max_q=5,
                             m=50,
                             seasonal=True,
                             d=None,
                             D=1,
                             trace=True,
                             error_action='ignore',
                             suppress_warnings=True,
                             stepwise=True)

auto_arima_fit.summary()
```

Performing stepwise search to minimize aic

```
ARIMA(2,0,1)(1,1,1)[50] intercept : AIC=inf, Time=36.17 sec
ARIMA(0,0,0)(0,1,0)[50] intercept : AIC=1531.494, Time=1.08 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(1,1,0)[50] intercept : AIC=1191.636, Time=5.43 sec
ARIMA(0,0,1)(0,1,1)[50] intercept : AIC=inf, Time=9.09 sec
ARIMA(0,0,0)(0,1,0)[50] : AIC=1529.504, Time=0.22 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(0,1,0)[50] intercept : AIC=1357.220, Time=1.13 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(2,1,0)[50] intercept : AIC=inf, Time=16.31 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(1,1,1)[50] intercept : AIC=inf, Time=13.51 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(0,1,1)[50] intercept : AIC=inf, Time=10.50 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(2,1,1)[50] intercept : AIC=inf, Time=33.60 sec
ARIMA(0,0,0)(1,1,0)[50] intercept : AIC=1360.294, Time=3.93 sec
ARIMA(2,0,0)(1,1,0)[50] intercept : AIC=1192.922, Time=6.72 sec
ARIMA(1,0,1)(1,1,0)[50] intercept : AIC=1192.984, Time=6.35 sec
ARIMA(0,0,1)(1,1,0)[50] intercept : AIC=1217.240, Time=5.61 sec
ARIMA(2,0,1)(1,1,0)[50] intercept : AIC=1194.801, Time=22.78 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(1,1,0)[50] : AIC=1189.640, Time=2.40 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(0,1,0)[50] : AIC=1355.234, Time=0.27 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(2,1,0)[50] : AIC=inf, Time=6.59 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(1,1,1)[50] : AIC=inf, Time=10.66 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(0,1,1)[50] : AIC=inf, Time=7.29 sec
ARIMA(1,0,0)(2,1,1)[50] : AIC=inf, Time=23.79 sec
ARIMA(0,0,0)(1,1,0)[50] : AIC=1358.298, Time=1.10 sec
ARIMA(2,0,0)(1,1,0)[50] : AIC=1190.927, Time=3.06 sec
ARIMA(1,0,1)(1,1,0)[50] : AIC=1190.989, Time=3.19 sec
ARIMA(0,0,1)(1,1,0)[50] : AIC=1215.251, Time=2.64 sec
ARIMA(2,0,1)(1,1,0)[50] : AIC=1192.806, Time=7.82 sec
```

Best model: ARIMA(1,0,0)(1,1,0)[50]

Total fit time: 241.258 seconds

Out[533...]

SARIMAX Results

Dep. Variable:	y	No. Observations:	730
Model:	SARIMAX(1, 0, 0)x(1, 1, 0, 50)	Log Likelihood	-591.820
Date:	Sat, 08 Jan 2022	AIC	1189.640

Time:	23:51:03	BIC	1203.207
Sample:	0	HQIC	1194.892
	- 730		
Covariance Type:	opg		

	coef	std err	z	P> z	[0.025	0.975]
ar.L1	-0.4714	0.035	-13.647	0.000	-0.539	-0.404
ar.S.L50	-0.4813	0.034	-14.243	0.000	-0.548	-0.415
sigma2	0.3273	0.018	18.291	0.000	0.292	0.362

Ljung-Box (L1) (Q):	0.17	Jarque-Bera (JB):	3.06
Prob(Q):	0.68	Prob(JB):	0.22
Heteroskedasticity (H):	1.13	Skew:	0.16
Prob(H) (two-sided):	0.37	Kurtosis:	3.00

Warnings:

[1] Covariance matrix calculated using the outer product of gradients (complex-step).

In [653...

```
# Build SARIMAX model (Final model)
model = sm.tsa.SARIMAX(df_train,
                       order=(1, 0, 0),
                       seasonal_order=(1, 1, 0, 50), trend='c',
                       freq=df_train.index.freq)

SARIMAX_results = model.fit()

# Print results tables
print(SARIMAX_results.summary())
```

```

SARIMAX Results
=====
=====
Dep. Variable:          Revenue    No. Observations:
545
Model:                SARIMAX(1, 0, 0)x(1, 1, 0, 50)    Log Likelihood          -4
25.486
Date:                 Mon, 10 Jan 2022    AIC                      8
58.971
Time:                 19:54:12          BIC                      8
75.790
Sample:               01-03-2020          HQIC                     8
65.574
                    - 06-30-2021
Covariance Type:          opg
=====
=====
                    coef    std err          z      P>|z|      [0.025    0.975]
-----
intercept            -0.0163     0.026       -0.621     0.535     -0.068     0.035

```

```

ar.L1      -0.4777    0.039   -12.131    0.000    -0.555    -0.400
ar.S.L50   -0.5136    0.039   -13.011    0.000    -0.591    -0.436
sigma2     0.3166    0.021    15.084    0.000    0.275     0.358

```

```

=====
Ljung-Box (L1) (Q):      0.19   Jarque-Bera (JB):      0.82
Prob(Q):                0.66   Prob(JB):              0.66
Heteroskedasticity (H): 1.14   Skew:                  0.08
Prob(H) (two-sided):    0.39   Kurtosis:              2.87
=====

```

Warnings:

[1] Covariance matrix calculated using the outer product of gradients (complex-step).

In [654...

```

# Plot common diagnostics
SARIMAX_results.plot_diagnostics(figsize=(10, 6))
plt.show()

```


In [655...

```

# Create SARIMA mean forecast
sarima_forecast = SARIMAX_results.get_forecast()
sarima_mean = sarima_forecast.predicted_mean
sarima_conf_int = sarima_forecast.conf_int(alpha=0.05)
sarima_se = sarima_forecast.se_mean

```

In [656...

```

print('95% Confidence Interval between %.2f and %.2f' % (sarima_conf_int['lower Revenue'], sarima_conf_int['upper Revenue']))
print('Mean: %.2f' % sarima_mean)
print('Standard Error: %.2f' % sarima_se)

```

95% Confidence Interval between -1.43 and 0.77

Mean: -0.33

Standard Error: 0.56

In [657...

```

# Predict with respect to test set and visualization

start = '6-30-2021'
end = '12-31-2021'

predictions = SARIMAX_results.predict(start, end, type = 'levels').rename('Predictions')
fig, ax = plt.subplots()
df_test.plot(label = 'Test', figsize=(15, 4), ax=ax)
predictions.plot(label = 'Predictions', figsize=(15, 4), ax=ax)
plt.title('Revenue Predictions')
plt.xlabel('Day')
plt.ylabel('Actual Revenue')
plt.legend(loc='upper left', fontsize = 8)
ax.legend(labels=['Test', 'Predictions'])
plt.show()
# Create an axis

```


In [659...

```

# model Evaluation

# Mean Squared Error
MSE = mean_squared_error(df_test['Revenue'], predictions)
print('MSE: ', round(MSE, 4))
# Root Mean Squared Error
RMSE = rmse(df_test['Revenue'], predictions)
print('RMSE: ', round(RMSE, 4))

```

MSE: 0.3777

RMSE: 0.6146

Part V: Data Summary and Implications

Summarize your findings and assumptions:

The Data Analysis study used the auto_arima to generate the optimal p, d, and q values; the auto_arima model selected the values (1,0,0) (1,1,0,50) as the optimal values based on the lowest AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) 1189.640.

Using the standard 95% confidence interval, the study results were only a %5 likelihood that the real observation will fail outside the range -1.43 and 0.77.

The study spitted most of the dataset about 18 months as training data and just the last 6 months as test data and using the test data to compare the results with the forecasting data to

give the decision-makers the chance to compare and plan for the forecasting, more data and more analysis will improve the forecasting results.

SARIMA Model evaluation for each predicted and actual displays Mean square error (MSE) 0.37 and Root Mean square error (RMSE) 0.61, which reflects high confidence in the model accuracy.

Recommended a course of action: the decision-makers could use the study to define patterns of revenue forecasting, and the data analyst could run more tests on more data to improve the model results.

Acknowledge Sources:

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PSU. (2021, Dec. 21) Autocorrelation and Time Series. [Web Site]. Retrieved from <https://online.stat.psu.edu/stat462/node/188/>

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Kaggle. (2022, Jan. 9) Notebook, Time series analysis. [Web Site]. Retrieved from <https://www.kaggle.com/urayukitaka/notebook-time-series-analysis>

In []: